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SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT AS A PREREQUISITE FOR FUTURE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION SPECIALISTS' BECOMING

РОЗВИТОК СОЦІОКУЛЬТУРНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНЦІЇ ЯК ПЕРЕДУМОВА СТАНОВЛЕННЯ МАЙБУТНІХ ФАХІВЦІВ ПУБЛІЧНОГО УПРАВЛІННЯ ТА АДМІНІСТРУВАННЯ

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Балан О.С., Шепель М.Є. Розвиток соціокультурної компетенції як передумова становлення майбутніх фахівців галузі публічного управління та адміністрування. Науково-методична стаття.

Статтю присвячено розвитку соціокультурної компетенції як передумові становлення майбутніх державних службовців у процесі вивчення іноземної мови. Метою статті виступило визначити роль соціокультурної компетенції у процесі професійної підготовки майбутніх фахівців публічного управління. Авторами статті зроблено аналіз вітчизняних та зарубіжних джерел присвячених питанню соціокультурної компетенції, професійної етики, ділового мовленнєвого етикету, викладанню іноземної мови у немовних вишах, становленню майбутніх професіоналів. Автори надають власне визначення поняттям «соціокультурна компетенція», «діловий мовленнєвий етикет». Запропоновано модель щодо розвитку соціокультурної компетенції майбутніх фахівців галузі публічного управління та адміністрування як оффлайн так і онлайн.

Ключові слова: соціокультурна компетенція, фахівець, публічне управління та адміністрування, заняття з іноземної мови, діловий мовленнєвий етикет

Balan O.S., Shepel M.Ye. Sociocultural Competence Development as Prerequisite for Future Public Administration Specialists' Becoming. Scientific and methodological article.

The article deals with sociocultural competence development as prerequisite of future civil servants' becoming in the process of learning a foreign language. The aim of the article was to define the role of sociocultural competence in the process of future public administration specialists' professional training. The authors of the article have made the analysis of domestic and foreign resources devoted to the issues of sociocultural competence, professional ethics, business speech etiquette, teaching foreign languages at non-linguistic universities, future professionals' becoming. The authors give their own notion to the concepts "sociocultural competence", "business speech etiquette". The model for public administration specialists' sociocultural competence development both offline and online are proposed.

Keywords: sociocultural competence, a future specialist, public administration, a foreign language tutorial, business speech etiquette

The development of Ukraine as an independent democratic state, its integration into the European Community, strengthening ties with the world's leading countries requires public administration specialists' training who are able to represent our country in the international arena. It means that we need all round professionals who obtain both special knowledge (related to their job area) and soft skills (creative thinking, teamwork, communication, problems solving, work, conflict resolution). As public administration specialists' activity is connected with working with different people, business trips, knowing foreign languages and cultural norms of other countries becomes very crucial. "The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment" states that the main aim of a foreign language teaching is mastering the language as a way of intercultural communication, skills development to use a foreign language as a tool in the cultures and civilizations dialogue in the modern world. The communicative competence background consists of communicative skills, which are formed on the basis of speech knowledge and skills, sociocultural and sociolinguistic knowledge, skills [20]. As it can be seen, intercultural communication consists not only communicative skills but also sociocultural and sociolinguistic knowledge. Thus, future public administration specialists' sociocultural competence development becomes relevant.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

In the research papers of Ukrainian and foreign scientists one can find different viewpoints devoted to sociocultural competence: O. Havrilova [6], R. Kelembet, O. Peycheva [8], A. Bogush [3], O. Tarnauz [16],

U.I. Kopzhasarova, B.A. Beisenbaeva, A.T. Kikimova [9], S. Amelina, L. Azzolini, V. Hamanyuk, N. Zhdanova [1], S.Kukharonok, I. Svyrydenko [10], V. Mynka [11], K.Nihametianova [13], O. Khunoi, A. Boudjelal [23]; professional ethics and business speech etiquette: S. Amelina [2], I. Bostan, C.Costuleanu, E. Horomnea, M. Costuleanu [20], O. Bratkova [4], M. Ogrenich [14], V. Vetrinskaya, T. Dmitrenko [26], teaching foreign languages at non-linguistic universities: A. Bagateeva, Yu. Ryseieva, A. Vasylieva, R. Haraieva [19], N. Bulharu [5], C.G. Gökhan Cansiz [23], L. Moroz, A. Dubrova, V. Trofimchuk [12], S. Muntian [25], L. Varečková, J. Pavelková [27]; the issues of future specialists' becoming, professional orientation and development: S. Alaghmand, F. Mozaffar, S.B. Hosseini, B.S. Sedghpour [18], H. Yavorska [17].

Unsolved aspects of the problem

However, the analysis of scientific, psychological and pedagogical literature has shown that not enough attention is paid to future civil servants' sociocultural competence development.

The aim of the article is to define the role of sociocultural competence in future public administration specialists' professional training.

The main part

Branching the concepts of "competence" and "competency" is important in our study. In the reference literature, "competence" is defined as a good knowledge of something, the scope of authority of any organization, institution or a person [14, p.874]. The Glossary of the European Training Foundation regards competence as "as the ability to do something well, effectively in accordance with the employment requirements, as the ability to perform special job functions" [7, p.63] and four competence models are given: "the model on personality parameters; the model for solving problems; the productive activity model; the performance management model" [6, p.69]. The notion of "competent" is distinguished as: who has sufficient knowledge in any field; who is well acquainted with something; clever; who is based on knowledge; qualified; who has certain powers; full-fledged; sovereign [13, p.874]. Thus, competency can be considered as a good awareness in any field. Competency is the ability to fulfill a certain activity, it's a person's professional quality, a person's ability to obtain a competence in the professional activity. Competence is developed during vocational training in the form of knowledge, skills and abilities. So competence can be defined as the process of obtaining knowledge, and competency is the result of applying knowledge.

The European Union defines the following key competences for lifelong learning: (1) Literacy competence; (2) Multilingual competence; (3) Mathematical competence and competence in science, technology and engineering; (4) Digital competence; (5) Personal, social and learning to learn competence; (6) Citizenship competence; (7) Entrepreneurship competence and (8) Cultural awareness and expression competence [22].

In our opinion, all competencies are urgent for a future civil servant's personality formation. However, in our study we will consider socio-cultural competence as one of the important components of a specialist's professional training and becoming.

When considering the problem of sociocultural competence, scientists came to the following conclusions

Thus, V. Mynka considers sociocultural competence as knowledge of native speakers' cultural features, their habits, traditions, norms of behaviour and etiquette and the ability to understand foreign language speakers' communicative behaviour and adequately use the acquired knowledge in communication while remaining a native speaker of another culture [11, p.161].

According to the definition of U. Kopzhasarova, B. Beisenbayeva, A. Kikimova, sociocultural competence presupposes knowing the national-cultural features of native speakers' social and linguistic introduction and means to use them in the communication process. This competence formation is carried out in the context of cultural dialogue, allows to achieve intercultural understanding between people and their tolerant attitude formation towards another culture [9, p.1406].

Linguists S. Amelina, L. Azzolini, V. Hamanyuk and N. Zhdanova consider sociocultural competence as a communicative competency component. They understand students' ability to realize, adequately evaluate and interpret sociocultural information expressed explicitly and implicitly at different semantic levels of authentic foreign language meaning publicistic (newspaper-magazine article) or literary text, in an environment of indirect, mass and intercultural communication, based on the system of relevant knowledge, skills and abilities developed in students [1].

According to O. Tarnauz, sociocultural competence is knowledge, the ability to use foreign the language sociocultural realities in communication and cognition. The scientist divides sociocultural competence into cross-cultural competence, which contains knowledge about a country's culture of whose language is being studied (knowledge of history, geography, economy, state system, traditions) and ethnolinguistic competence. The latter one involves students' mastery of speech and non-speech behaviour features of native speakers in certain communication situations [16, p.312].

S. Kukharonok and I. Svyrydenko consider that sociocultural competence characterizes the self-development process of a person's personality, which is based on the one hand on an individual's ability to accumulate knowledge, and on the other hand- the ability to analyze sociocultural phenomena, understand and explain them, to make analogies and associations between different areas of knowledge. It also promotes behavioural values and norms that enhance the desire and ability to take responsibility for personal activities [10, p.73].

O Khonui, A.Boudjelal regard sociocultural competence as having enough knowledge about the target language culture and social norms to be able to communicate effectively in that language and to behave appropriately in the target language society. This competence is considered crucially important for the reason that language is deeply affected by its culture, and its utterances can hardly be free from any cultural interpretations [24, p.439]. The scientists emphasize that having this competence is of crucial importance for FL (foreign language) and SL (second language) learners, as it refers to having adequate knowledge about the social and cultural rules that are conventional in the target language society such as the level of formality when addressing others, non-verbal communication (eye contact, gestures, facial expressions, tone of speech, speed of delivery and length of silence or pause before turn-taking) [24, p.440]. Thus communicative competence development becomes of great importance. The linguodidact A. Bogush understands communicative competence as a complex use by the speaker of linguistic and non-linguistic means for communication in concrete social and everyday situations, ability to be guided in a speech situation, initiative in communication; human awareness, a certain system of knowledge, practical speech skills, a person's speech abilities [3, p.102].

According to O. Havrilova, sociocultural competence primarily contributes to evaluating common and distinctive features between cultures, helps to distinguish prejudices and get rid of them, charges a tolerant attitude towards other cultures, and creates a basis for intercultural exchanges. Students' sociocultural competence acquisition determines their ability to adjust their own behaviour in accordance with the characteristics and norms of another country [6, p.377].

We support O. Havrilova's position on the fact that when working with students of non-linguistic profile in sociocultural competence formation, important attention is paid to general cultural and cross-cultural (culturological) competencies (factual knowledge about the country, people, mentality, socio-political system, basic geographical, demographic, political data, information about prominent figures, cultural achievements, life, traditions, etc.). In practice, they can be applied through social competence, i.e. the ability to enter into effective communicative relationships with other people, navigate in a constantly changing communicative situation; take into account the peculiarities of etiquette and nonverbal behaviour, behavioural social norms and social status of communication participants) [6, p.377-378].

As it is stated by K. Nigametzyanova, sociocultural competence includes the following components: linguistic component (possession of lexical units and phraseology with national-cultural semantics), sociolinguistic component (language features knowledge of a social class, social groups, as well as dialectical variants); socio-psychological component (knowledge of sign language, behavioural patterns and communication techniques that are specific to a particular culture and territory); culturological aspect (the need development for subjects to deepen their knowledge of the people' traditions, habits, history of whose language is being studied) [13, p.100].

Thus, analysing the scientists' positions concerning sociocultural competence one can highlight its structure, which is presented in Table 1

Analysing the scholars' viewpoints we understand future public administration specialists' sociocultural competence as combination of competences: cross-cultural (knowledge of a country's traditions, socio-political system, general geographical, demographic, political data); communicative (applying verbal and non-verbal means of communication depending on the environment); ethnolinguistic (possessing lexical units and phraseology; knowledge of native speakers' speech and non-speech behaviour features in certain communicative situations).

In our opinion, sociocultural competence is connected with speech etiquette. As it is known, a civil servant's career is connected with communication. And in its turn communication means knowledge of speech clichés, business speech etiquette.

According to the position of I. Bostan, C. Costuleanu, E. Horromnea and M. Costuleanu the expression "business ethics" focuses every good, equitable, correct and true element that is present in the assembly of institutions, transactions or efforts, generically called businesses [20, p.49].

O. Bratkova highlights that professional ethics is first and foremost a specific code of ethics for people in a particular profession. Each profession puts forward appropriate moral requirements to the people who have chosen it, and it creates special moral problems [4, p.89]. The scholar emphasizes the basic moral and ethical norms that promote effective professional interaction and communication, namely: integrity, honesty, objectivity, tolerance, respect, responsibility, etc. [4, p.91].

As M. Ogrenich notes, business speech etiquette involves using the established speech formulae in certain forms of business communication (business telephony, business conversations and sessions, meetings, rallies, negotiations, discussions, debates) and the main business communication situations (acquaintance, greetings, business cards, image creation, exchanging gifts, etc.) [15, p.10]. The scientist has made a comparative analysis of the national and cultural specifics of Ukrainian and English speech etiquette, which noted that in the business communication culture in both languages there are many similarities. The scholar states that at the same time, there are speech etiquette national features, characterized by a set of standard clichés of business communication in each language, etiquette formulae for starting, conducting, maintaining, ending a business conversation, telephone clichés, and so on. Such clichés are used by native speakers only in professional communication related to the official duties performance, normative rules of verbal and nonverbal behaviour in the field of business communication [15, p.10-11].

Table 1. The Sociocultural Competence Structure

Sociocultural Competence	
Components	Indicators
Cross-cultural/culturological competence	knowledge of history, geography, economy, state system, traditions; factual knowledge about the country, people, mentality, socio-political system, basic geographical, demographic, political data, information about prominent figures, cultural achievements, life, traditions, etc
Ethnolinguistic competence/ component	Students' mastery of speech and non-speech behaviour features of native speakers in certain communication situations.
	Possessing lexical units and phraseology with national-cultural semantics
Social competence	Ability to enter into effective communicative relationships with other people, navigate in a constantly changing communicative situation; take into account the peculiarities of etiquette and nonverbal behaviour, behavioural social norms and social status of communication participants
Communicative competence	complex use by the speaker of linguistic and non-linguistic means for communication in concrete social and everyday situations, ability to be guided in a speech situation, initiative in communication; human awareness, a certain system of knowledge, practical speech skills, a person's speech abilities
sociolinguistic component	language features knowledge of a social class, social groups, as well as dialectical variants
socio-psychological component	knowledge of sign language, behavioural patterns and communication techniques that are specific to a particular culture and territory
culturological aspect	the need development for subjects to deepen their knowledge of the people' traditions, habits, history of whose language is being studied

Source: compiled by autor on materials [3, 6, 13, 16, 24].

According to V. Vertinskaya and T. Dmitrenko speech etiquette is an important component of business culture. Following the rules of speech etiquette maintains the positive reputation of the whole organization. Lack of necessary knowledge of speech etiquette, which constitutes a kind of background in a communicative act, can lead to misunderstanding in the process of communication between speakers of different languages and cultures. Speech etiquette in the narrow sense of the word can be described as a system of linguistic communication in which etiquette relations manifest themselves. Elements of this system can be implemented at different language levels [27, p.28].

Thus, we understand speech etiquette as an important part of speech culture, knowledge of etiquette formulae of business conversation, telephone conversation, language clichés, and mastery of verbal and nonverbal forms of communication depending on the environment.

We have found out that in accordance with the curriculum requirements in a foreign language, non-linguistic universities provide for the professionally oriented foreign language competence acquisition in the first and second study year, when students are in the process of acquiring knowledge in the particular specialty. We consider that learning a foreign language shouldn't be regarded as a particular subject, it must be an important component of professional training, based on interdisciplinary links of professional disciplines.

According to the Educational and Professional Programme on future public specialists' training (Bachelor's degree) students have to obtain the following general and special competencies during the educational process. We put the competencies and educational outcomes in the Table 2.

Analyzing the Table 2 we can see that both general and special competencies contain communicative competence which in turn includes sociocultural communicative competence, knowledge of ethical norms.

Bearing in mind, that at non-language universities students do not study ethnolinguistics where they are given information about the country whose language is studied and reflects the sociocultural, spiritual and personal component of the language material, in the process of learning a foreign language it is necessary to pay special attention to the students of non-linguistic universities with this language aspect. So when choosing the methodology of teaching the foreign (English) language aimed at sociocultural competence development, we have chosen the communicative approach. As it is known, this approach develops communicative processes, which in turn, motivate students to express their thoughts, emotions and feelings, show non-verbal behaviour and control it. Thus we have developed the model of sociocultural competence development with emphasis on communicatively-oriented learning. The model is presented in the Figure 1.

Table 2. General and Special Competencies that Students Obtain in the Educational Process

General competencies	Special competencies
GC 11 Ability to communicate a foreign language (EO 3 – Be able to communicate orally and in written form in a foreign language; EO 12 – be able to establish communication between citizens and public authorities and local self-government bodies.)	SC 1 Ability for social interaction, cooperation and conflict resolution (EO 7 – Be able to organize and participate in volunteer/cultural, educational/sports projects aimed at forming a healthy lifestyle/active citizenship; EO12 – Be able to establish communication between citizens and public authorities and local self-government bodies).
GC 12 Interpersonal skills (EO 7 – Be able to organize and participate in volunteer/cultural, educational/sports projects aimed at forming a healthy lifestyle/active citizenship; EO 12 – Be able to establish communication between citizens and public authorities and local self- government bodies)	SC 3. Ability to ensure compliance with legal and moral and ethical standards of behaviour (EO 3 – To apply norms and rules of professional communication in the Ukrainian language).
GC 13 Ability to communicate with representatives of other professional groups of different levels (with experts from other fields of knowledge/activities): EO 2 – To apply norms and rules of professional communication in the Ukrainian language. EO 3 – Be able to communicate orally and in written form in a foreign language; EO 12 – be able to establish communication between citizens and public authorities and local self- government bodies)	SC 9 Ability to introduce innovative technologies (EO 3 – Be able to communicate orally and in written form in a foreign language)
	SC 11 Ability in a working group to conduct applied research in the field of public administration (EO 12 – Be able to establish communication between citizens and public authorities and local self- government bodies.)

Source: authors' own development

Analysing the model we can see that sociocultural competence development model includes components (cross-cultural/culturologic; ethnolinguistic; social; communicative); competencies (GC: ability to communicate a foreign language; interpersonal skills; ability to communicate with representatives of other professional groups of different levels. SC: ability for social interaction, cooperation and conflict resolution; ability to ensure compliance with legal and moral and ethical standards of behaviour; ability to introduce innovative technologies; ability in a working group to conduct applied research in the field of public administration); topics (the English Language in Future Professional Activity; Multicultural World; Business Partners Meeting; Telephoning; Travellings; Public Administration Career; Human Resources; Government; Political Systems; The World Organizations; Constitution.; Law; Local Authority. City Managers; Local Governments; Budget. Taxes. Regulatory Economics; Urbanization; Rural Areas; Demography. Sociocultural competence development is implemented through the following methods: reading comprehension, business and role-playing games, case method, project method, brainstorming, vocabulary replenishment, "microphone". It can be seen from the model, components, competencies, topics and methods are in interrelation with each other.

Let's have a closer look to the methods of sociocultural competence development.

Reading comprehension includes working with professionally oriented texts. It plays an important role in the sociocultural competence development. In the process of this work we use pre-reading activities, while-reading activities and post-reading activities.

Thus, pre-reading activities are introduced in order to motivate our students to work with the material and overcome the difficulties of understanding professional terms, enlarging the students' vocabulary. For example, the students have to answer a question/ a group of questions, match the words with their meanings, find words translation in dictionary. During while-reading activities the students work with an original text. It's not only reading and translating the text. It can be matching heading with the paragraphs, putting extracts in the correct order. Post-reading activities are aimed at understanding the information read. For example, the students fill in the gaps, find the word/word combination in the text according to the explanation, match the word with its translation), answer the questions on the text.

Currently, we also use such a technique as skimming. The students look through the text and try to understand general information. In order to develop literacy, we set our students the task of composing different types of questions to the text, making dialogues on the text, a small public speech on the topic of the text.

During the development of future public administration specialists' sociocultural competence, we conduct business and role-playing games. The aim of these games is modelling students' future professional activities, playing situations connected with business speech etiquette, behaviour and communicative culture. For example, the students are given the task to act out short conversations on the topics. "Business Partners Meeting", "Booking a Flight/a Hotel/a Train Ticket", "On the Phone", "At the Airport/at the Train Station/at the Hotel". Students are given the instructions to follow speech etiquette rules, social and cultural rules of a country they "are in". During the games we develop such skills as trust and empathy, the ability to listen to future colleagues, subordinates and clients.

Figure 1 Sociocultural Development Model

Source: authors' own development

In the development of future professionals' logical and critical thinking, personal and professional qualities applying such methods as: case method, project method, brainstorming, vocabulary replenishment, "microphone" are of great importance.

Thus, the case method involves a comprehensive analysis of specific situations, their discussion and the students' acquaintance with different approaches to solving problems. The students are given a problem that they should solve, adhering to the rules of speech etiquette, knowledge of sociocultural characteristics of an organization/a city/ a country. For example, the students have to appoint a meeting with a partner who is always late, or they have to switch a meeting, cancel a hotel/flight/train, change tickets; cope with booking problems.

The project method is aimed to teach the students to look for necessary information. Students make PowerPoint presentations on the following topics: «Different Countries – Different Cultures», "Comparing Political Systems", "Urbanization Challenges", "World Organizations", "Economy in Ukraine and English Speaking Countries", "Demography". The students perform with the topic, spontaneously answering questions during the discussion.

Brainstorming helps to form thematically oriented questions that students can ask each other or in the process of group work. These questions are written on the blackboard. Each student has to answer them, and each answer is written on the board for further revision by students. During brainstorming students give ideas on the following topics "Demography", "Urbanization Challenges", "Future of World Organizations".

The vocabulary replenishment method is necessary to acquaint students with other countries' cultural characteristics. This method is carried out in the process of working with texts (new vocabulary implementation), performing lexical and grammatical tasks. Students are given the task to use new lexical units in their speeches.

The «microphone» method promotes the students' public speech development. The students make short speeches on the topic according to their curricula. This method reduces errors occurrence and helps to make inferences that are corrected by the teacher and students.

During our tutorials we pay special attention to listening skills development. Applying authentic audio and video materials play an important role in future specialists' sociocultural competence development. Thus, listening to audio materials contributes to the students' correct pronunciation, to distinguish aurally English dialects. Watching videos helps the students to create an idea of a country, its social and political system, cultural features.

Since the COVID-19 pandemic has made its adjustments to the teaching and educational process of training institutions at all levels, some of the tutorials are conducted online using video conferencing platforms. We use the Google Meet platform. We apply Google classroom to place materials for groups. Before classes, students are downloaded a particular material (texts, presentations, links to audio and video). In the course of online classes, texts for work and tasks for them are displayed on the screen, and the students can work with them directly from the monitor screen/gadget. Students also watch video, listen to audio online, and then complete

assignments for them. In the online learning process the students' ability to introduce their presentation on a specific topic becomes important. Everything happens the same way as in the auditorium. In role-playing and business games, students are taken to webinar rooms where they discuss issues in pairs or small groups. So, communicative skills can be developed both offline and online.

Conclusions

In our opinion, with the help of the abovementioned techniques and methods in the process of teaching a foreign language, students will not only gain knowledge and ideas about sociocultural competence, but also will be able to apply them in future professional activities. This methodology of sociocultural competence development in the process of teaching a foreign language will facilitate: the students' personal and significant qualities improvement, professionally important qualities development, behaviour skills formation in professional activity of future specialists in public administration taking into account cultural norms and rules of the other party. As we can see, sociocultural competence development in foreign language classes plays an important role in the future specialists in public administration formation. The proposed methods will promote the formation of communicative skills, empathy, improving professional and personal moral and ethical qualities of future professionals, which will not only affect the public administration development, but also the country's welfare of in general.

The problem of applying platforms for distance and online education in the process of future specialists' training needs further study.

Abstract

The development of Ukraine as an independent democratic state, its integration into the European Community, strengthening ties with the world's leading countries requires public administration specialists' training who are able to represent our country in the international arena. Nowadays language proficiency, knowing cultural norms of different countries are of great importance. The communicative competence background consist of communicative skills, which are formed on the basis of speech knowledge and skills, sociocultural and sociolinguistic knowledge, skills. Thus, future public administration specialists' sociocultural competence development of becomes relevant.

The aim of the article is to define the role of sociocultural competence in future public administration specialists' professional training.

Sociocultural competence of future specialists in public administration we understand as combination of competences: cross-cultural (knowledge of a country's traditions, socio-political system, general geographical, demographic, political data); communicative (applying verbal and non-verbal means of communication depending on the environment); ethnolinguistic (possessing lexical units and phraseology; knowledge of native speakers' speech and non-speech behaviour features in certain communicative situations.)

In our opinion, sociocultural competence is connected with speech etiquette. We understand speech etiquette as an important part of speech culture, knowledge of etiquette forms of business conversation, telephone conversation, language clichés, mastery of verbal and nonverbal forms of communication depending on the environment.

We have found out that in accordance with the the curriculum requirements in a foreign language, non-linguistic universities provide for the professionally oriented foreign language competence acquisition in the first and second study year, when students are in the process of acquiring knowledge in the particular specialty. We consider that learning a foreign language shouldn't be regarded as a particular subject, it must be an important component of professional training, based on interdisciplinary links of professional disciplines.

According to the Educational and Professional Programme on future public specialists' training (Bachelor's degree) students have to obtain the following general and special competencies during the educational process.

Bearing in mind, that at non-language universities students do not study ethnolinguistics where they are given information about the country whose language is studied and reflects the sociocultural, spiritual and personal component of the language material, in the process of learning a foreign language it is necessary to pay special attention to the students of non-linguistic universities with this language aspect. So when choosing the methodology of teaching the foreign (English) language aimed at sociocultural competence development, we have chosen the communicative approach. As it is known, this approach develops communicative processes, which in turn, motivates students to express their thoughts, emotions and feelings, show non-verbal behaviour and control it. Thus we have developed the model of sociocultural competence development with emphasis on communicatively-oriented learning.

In the development of future professionals' sociocultural competence we used such methods as reading comprehension case method, project method, brainstorming, vocabulary replenishment, «microphone» are of great importance.

Since the COVID-19 pandemic has made its adjustments to the teaching and educational process of training institutions at all levels, some of the tutorials are conducted online using video conferencing platforms.

Sociocultural competence development in foreign language classes plays an important role in the future specialists in public administration formation. The proposed methods will promote the formation of

communicative skills, empathy, improving professional and personal moral and ethical qualities of future professionals, which will not only affect the public administration development, but also the country's welfare of in general.

Список літератури:

1. Амеліна С.М. Рамкова програма з німецької мови професійного спілкування для вищих навчальних закладів України / С. М. Амеліна, Л. С. Аззоліні, В. А. Гаманюк, Н. С. Жданова. – К.: Ленвіт, 2014. – 136 с.
2. Амеліна С.М. Теоретико-методичні основи формування культури професійного спілкування студентів вищих аграрних навчальних закладів: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня д-ра пед. наук: спец.: 13.00.04 «Теорія і методика професійної освіти» / С. М. Амеліна. – Х., 2008. – С. 40.
3. Богуш А.Ф. Методика навчання української мови в дошкільних закладах: навч. посіб. / А. Ф. Богуш – Київ: Вища школа, 1993. – 327 с.
4. Браткова О.І. Проблема професійної взаємодії майбутнього фахівця крізь призму деонтології / О. І. Браткова // Педагогічна освіта: теорія і практика. Психологія. Педагогіка. – 2017. – № 27. – С. 86-90. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Potip_2017_27_19.
5. Булгару Н.Б. Специфіка іншомовної мовленнєвої підготовки студентів технічних ВНЗ / Н. Б. Булгару // Науковий вісник Миколаївського національного університету імені В.О. Сухомлинського. Серія: Педагогічні науки. – 2017. – № 4. – С. 80-84. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Nvmdup_2017_4_15.
6. Гаврилова О.В. Формування соціокультурної компетенції студентів нефілологічного профілю / О. В. Гаврилова // Молодий вчений. – 2017. – № 1. – С. 376-379. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/molv_2017_1_92.
7. Глоссарий терминов рынка труда, разработки стандартов, образовательных программ и учебных планов. Европейский фонд образования, 1997. – 145 с.
8. Келембет Р.В. Формування соціокультурної компетенції студентів на заняттях з англійської мови / Р. В. Келембет, О. О. Пейчева // Педагогічні науки: теорія, історія, інноваційні технології. – 2013. – № 5. – С. 239-245. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/pednauk_2013_5_29.
9. Копжасарова У.И. Развитие социокультурной компетенции учащихся на основе использования фразеологизмов английского и русского языков / У. И. Копжасарова, Б. А. Бейсенбаева, А. Т. Кикимова // European Researcher. – 2013. – Вып 50, № 4-5. – С. 1405-14011. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://www.ejournal.ru/journals_n/1370331851.pdf.
10. Кухарьонюк С. Формування лексичної соціокультурної компетенції студентів немовних спеціальностей ВНЗ / С. Кухарьонюк, І. Свириденко // Проблеми підготовки сучасного вчителя. – 2014. – № 10(1). – С. 71-76. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: [http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/ppsv_2014_10\(1\)_12](http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/ppsv_2014_10(1)_12).
11. Минка В.В. Джерела формування соціокультурної компетенції на заняттях з практики англійської мови / В. В. Минка // Наукові записки Національного університету «Острозька академія». Серія: Психологія і педагогіка. – 2010. – Вып. 15. – С. 160-164. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Nznuoapp_2010_15_30.
12. Мороз Л.В. Використання інноваційних технологій у процесі іншомовної підготовки студентів немовних спеціальностей / Л. В. Мороз, А. С. Дуброва, В. М. Трофімчук // Оновлення змісту, форм та методів навчання і виховання в закладах освіти. – 2016. – Вып. 14. – С. 86-89. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Ozfm_2016_14_25.
13. Нігаметзянова К. Формування соціокультурної компетенції на заняттях з іноземної мови професійного спілкування у вищих військових навчальних закладах / К. Нігаметзянова // Педагогічні науки. – 2016. – Вып. 66-67. – С. 99-104. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/pena_2016_66-67_17.
14. Новый тлумачний словник української мови у трьох томах. Том 1 // [авт.-уклад. проф. В. В. Яременко]. – К.: Аконіт, 2003. – 926 с.
15. Огреніч М.А. Формування мовленнєвого етикету в майбутніх економістів в англійськомовному діловому спілкуванні: автореф. дис. на здобуття наук. ступеня д-ра пед. наук: спец.13. 00.02 «Теорія та методика навчання (германські мови)» / М. А. Огреніч – О., 2011. – 20 с.
16. Тарнауз О.І. Розвиток соціокультурної компетентності / О. І. Тарнауз // Сучасні інформаційні технології та інноваційні методики навчання в підготовці фахівців: методологія, теорія, досвід, проблеми. – 2016. – Вып. 46. – С. 310-314. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Sitimm_2016_46_80.
17. Яворська Г.Х. Соціально-професійна зрілість курсантів вищих закладів освіти МВС України: [монографія] / Г. Х. Яворська. – О.: Пласке ЗАТ, 2005. – 408 с.
18. Alaghmand S. Investigating Factors Affecting Students' Self Actualization at University Spaces / S. Alaghmand, F. Mozaffar, S.B.Hosseini, B.S. Sedghpour // Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie

- Multidimensională. – 2018 – Vol. 10 (1-Special Issue 1), – P 1-7. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/32>.
19. Bagateeva A.O The Peculiarities of Foreign Language Training of Technical University Students in Conditions of Competence Approach / A. O. Bagateeva, Y. V. Ryseva, A. A. Vasilyeva, R. S. Garaeva // *Sovremennye Issledovaniya Sotsialnykh Problem*. – 2018 – Vol 9(3). – P. 16 – 27. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.12731/2218-7405-2018-3-16-27>.
 20. Bostan I. Morality, Ethics and True Image in Business Accounting / I.Bostan, C. Costuleanu, E. Horomnea, M.Costuleanu // *Theoretical and Applied Economics* – 2011. – Vol. 18. – P. 47-54. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227364503_Morality_Ethics_and_True_Image_in_Business_Accounting.
 21. Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment. Companion Volume with New Descriptors. Language Policy Programme - Council of Europe, 2018 – 235 p. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://rm.coe.int/cefr-companion-volume-with-new-descriptors-2018/1680787989>.
 22. European Commission (EC). Proposal for a council recommendation on key competences for lifelong learning. SWD. 14 final. Brussels: European Commission, 2018. – 104 p. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52018SC0014&from=EN>.
 23. Gökhan Cansiz C.G. Language Learning Strategies: An Holistic View / C. G. Gökhan Cansiz // *Special Issue: Psychology in Language Learning 2* – 2015. – Vol. 5(3). – P. 473-493. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssl.2015.5.3.7>.
 24. Khuoni O. Introducing the Target Language Culture to EFL Learners to Enhance Sociocultural Competence / O. Khuoni, A. Boudjelal // *Arab World English Journal*. – 2019. – Vol. 10 (3). – P. 438-447. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no3.31>.
 25. Muntian S. Students' Feedback in the Foreign Language Teaching: a Systems Theory Perspective / S. Muntian // *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensională* – 2017 – Vol. 9(2). – P. 48–55. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/2017.0902.03>.
 26. Varečková, L., & Pavelková, J. Importance of Foreign Languages in Education Process at Universities / L. Varečková, J.Pavelková // *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensională*. – 2018, Vol.10(4). – P. 294-306. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/89>.
 27. Vetrinskaya V.V Developing students' sociocultural competence in foreign language classes / V. V Vetrinskaya, T. A. Dmitrenko // *Training, Language and Culture*. – 2017. – Vol. 1(2). – P. 22-39. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://doi.org/10.29366/2017tlc.1.2.2>.

References:

1. Amelina, S.M., Azzolini, L.S., Hamanyuk, V.A., & Zhdanova, N.S. (2014). *Ramkova prohrama z nimetskoj movy profesiinoho spilkuvannia dlia vyshchykh navchalnykh zakladiv Ukrainy*. Kyiv: Lenvit [in Ukrainian].
2. Amelina, S.M. (2008). *Teoretyko-metodychni osnovy formuvannia kultury profesiinoho spilkuvannia studentiv vyshchykh ahrarnykh navchalnykh zakladiv* [Theoretical and Methodological Basis for Forming Cultured Professional Communication Skills in Students of Agrarian Higher Educational Institutions. Extended abstract of doctor's thesis. Kharkiv National Pedagogical University named after G.S. Skovoroda [in Ukrainian].
3. Bogush, A.M. (1993). *Metodyka navchannia ukrainskoj movy v doshkilnykh zakladakh*. Kyiv: Vyscha shkola [in Ukrainian].
4. Bratkova, O.I. (2017). *Problema profesiinoy vziaemodii maibutnoho fakhivtsia kriz pryzmu deontolohii*. [Problem of Future Specialist's Professional Interaction Through Deontology Prism]. *Pedahohichna osvita: teoriia i praktyka. Psykholohiia. Pedahohika*, 27, 86-90. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Potip_2017_27_19.
5. Bulharu, N.B. (2017). *Spetsyfika inshomovnoi movlennievoi pidhotovky studentiv tekhnichnykh VNZ* [Specificity of foreign language speech training of students of technical universities]. *Naukovyi visnyk Mykolaiivskoho natsionalnoho universytetu imeni V. O. Sukhomlyns'koho. Seriya: Pedahohichni nauky*, 4(59), 80-84. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Nvmdup_2017_4_15.
6. Havrylova, O.V. (2017). *Formuvannia sotsiokulturnoi kompetentsii studentiv nefilolohichnoho profilu* [Formation of Sociocultural Competence in Students Who Are Not Philologists]. *Molodyi vchenyi*, 1, 376-379. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/molv_2017_1_92 [in Ukrainian].
7. *Glossarij terminov rynku truda, razrobotki standartov, obrazovatel'nyh programm i uchebnyh planov* (1997). *Evropejskij fond obrazovaniya* [in Russian].
8. Kelembet, R.V. & Peycheva, O.O. (2013). *Formuvannia sotsiokulturnoi kompetentsii studentiv na zaniattiakh z anhliiskoi movy* [Students' Social and Cultural Competence Formation at the English

- classes] *Pedahohichni nauky: teoriia, istoriia, innovatsiini tekhnolohii*, 5, 239-245. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/pednauk_2013_5_29.
9. Kopzhasarova, U.I., Beisenbaeva, B.A., & Kikimova, A.T. (2013). Razvitie sociokul'turnoj kompetencii uchashchihsya na osnove ispol'zovaniya frazeologizmov anglijskogo i russkogo yazykov [Students' Socio-cultural Competence Development, Using English and Russian Phraseological Units]. *European Researcher*, 50(4-5), 1405-14011. Retrieved from http://www.erjournal.ru/journals_n/1370331851.pdf [in Russian].
 10. Kukharonok, S. & Svyrydenko, I. (2014). Formuvannia leksychnoi sotsiokulturnoi kompetentsii studentiv nemovnykh spetsialnestei VNZ. *Problemy pidhotovky suchasnoho vchytelia*, 10(1), 71-76. Retrieved from [http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/ppsv_2014_10\(1\)_12](http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/ppsv_2014_10(1)_12) [in Ukrainian].
 11. Mynka, V.V. (2010). Dzherela formuvannia sotsiokulturnoi kompetentsii na zaniattiakh z praktyky anhliiskoi movy. *Naukovi zapysky Natsionalnoho universytetu Ostrozka akademiia*". Serii: Psykholohiia i pedahohika, 15, 160-164. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Nzn_uoapp_2010_15_30.
 12. Moroz, L.V., Dubrova, A.S. & Trofimchuk, V.M. (2016). Vykorystannia innovatsiinykh tekhnolohii u protsesi inshomovnoi pidhotovky studentiv nemovnykh spetsialnestei [The use of innovative technology in foreign language training of students of nonlinguistic specialties]. *Onovlennia zmistu, form ta metodiv navchannia i vykhovannia v zakladakh osvity*, 14(57), 86-89. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Ozfm_2016_14_25 [in Ukrainian].
 13. Nigametzyanova, K. (2016). Formuvannia sotsiokulturnoi kompetentsii na zaniattiakh z inozemnoi movy profesiinoho spilkuvannia u vyshchykh viiskovykh navchalnykh zakladakh [Sociocultural Competence Development at the Lessons of English for Professional Communication in Military Higher Educational Establishments]. *Pedahohichni nauky*, 66-67, 99-104. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/pena_2016_66-67_17 [in Ukrainian].
 14. Yaremenko, V.V. (Ed.). (2003). *Novyi tlumachnyi slovnyk ukrainskoi movy u trokh tomakh*. Volume 1. Kyiv: Akonit.
 15. Ogrenich, M.A. (2011). Formuvannia movlennievoho etyketu v maibutnikh ekonomistiv v anhlo-movnomu dilovomu spilkuvanni [Future Economists' Speech Etiquette Development for Business English Communication]. Extended abstract of candidate's thesis. State Institution "South-Ukrainian National Pedagogical University named after K. D. Ushynskiy".
 16. Tarnauz, O.I. (2016). Rozvytok sotsiokulturnoi kompetentnosti [Sociocultural Competence Development]. *Suchasni informatsiini tekhnolohii ta innovatsiini metodyky navchannia v pidhotovtsi fakhivtsiv: metodolohiia, teoriia, dosvid, problem*, 46, 310-314. Retrieved from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Sitimn_2016_46_80 [in Ukrainian].
 17. Yavorska, H.Kh. (2005). *Sotsialno-profesiina zrilist kursantiv vyshchykh zakladiv osvity MVS Ukrainy: monograph*. Odessa: Plaske ZAT.
 18. Alaghmand, S., Mozaffar, F., Hosseini, S.B., & Sedghpour, B.S. (2018). Investigating Factors Affecting Students' Self-Actualization at University Spaces. *Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 10 (1-Special Issue 1), 1-7. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/32>.
 19. Bagateeva, A.O., Ryseva, Y.V., Vasilyeva, A.A., & Garaeva, R.S. (2018). The peculiarities of foreign language training of technical university students in conditions of competence approach. *Sovremennye Issledovaniya Sotsialnykh Problem*, 9(3), 16. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.12731/2218-7405-2018-3-16-27>.
 20. Bostan, I., Costuleanu, C., Horomnea, E., & Costuleanu, M. (2011). Morality, Ethics and True Image in Business Accounting. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, 18 (6), 47-54. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227364503_Morality_Ethics_and_True_Image_in_Business_Accounting.
 21. Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment. Companion Volume with New Descriptors. Language Policy Programme (2018). Council of Europe. Retrieved from <https://rm.coe.int/cefr-companion-volume-with-new-descriptors-2018/1680787989>.
 22. European Commission (EC) (2018). Proposal for a council recommendation on key competences for lifelong learning. SWD 14 final. Brussels: European Commission. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52018SC0014&from=EN>.
 23. Gökhan Cansiz, C.G. (2015). Language learning strategies: An holistic view. *Special Issue: Psychology in Language Learning* 2, 5(3), 473-493. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssl.2015.5.3.7>.
 24. Khounoi, O., & Boudjelal, A. (2019). Introducing the Target Language Culture to EFL Learners to Enhance Sociocultural Competence. *Arab World English Journal*, 10 (3) 438-447. Retrieved from <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol10no3.31>.
 25. Muntian, S. (2017). Students' Feedback in the Foreign Language Teaching: a Systems Theory Perspective. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 9(2), 48-55. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/2017.0902.03>.

26. Varečková, L., & Pavelková, J. (2018). Importance of Foreign Languages in Education Process at Universities. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 10(4), 294-306. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/89>.
27. Vetrinskaya, V.V., & Dmitrenko, T.A. (2017). Developing Students' Sociocultural Competence in Foreign Language Classes. *Training, Language and Culture*, 1(2), 22-39. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.29366/2017tlc.1.2.2>.

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